

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

Georgia Konstantopoulou¹, Maria Ioakeimidi², Konstantinos Assimakopoulos³, Evangelia Eirini Tsermpini⁴

¹Special Office for Health Consulting Services and Department of Education and Social Work, School of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Patras, Greece

²Department of Philosophy, Pedagogy and Psychology, School of Philosophy, University of Athens, Greece

³Department of Psychiatry, General University Hospital of Patras, University of Patras, Greece

⁴Laboratory of Pharmacogenomics and Personalized Treatment, Department of Pharmacy, University of Patras, Greece

ABSTRACT

When we talk about psychosis and psychotic disorders, we have in mind patients with disorganized thinking, mental retardation, delusions, and other similar symptoms associated with damage to the brain's normal functioning. Psychosis, however, is not the only cause of dysfunction, the abnormal functioning of the brain. The onset of psychosis may be due to psychological factors, with stress to be one of the main factors. Psychological and environmental factors interact with biological ones creating fertile ground for the development of psychosis. Anxiety, stress, depression, immigration, social stress, and consequently stressful life events are the leading causes of a psychotic episode. In this article, we will try to examine the following parameters: 1) what are the psychological-environmental factors that contribute to the onset of psychosis, and 2) what is their relationship with biological factors.

KEYWORDS: Anxiety, psychosis, hippocampus

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
19 November 2021

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org>

INTRODUCTION

Psychosis or psychotic disorder is defined as a psychiatric condition that describes a mental state long intertwined with hallucinations, delusions, and constant mental retardation. Patients with psychosis show a lack of normal behavior and a continuous loss of contact with reality for long periods, often with the onset of anxiety disorders. The causes of psychosis can come from different directions:

- Pathological changes in the structure and chemistry of the brain with consequent impairment of brain

function can cause the onset of psychosis in terms of the organic part of the disease (Figure 1).

- Another direction is the primary psychiatric condition and the type of the psychotic disorder or genetic predisposition. Anxiety and depression can cause psychosis.
- In addition, general medical conditions, hormones, sleep, or substance use can cause psychosis

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

Figure 1. Damage to the cerebral cortex (Aleman, A., Agrawal, N., Morgan, K.D., David, A.S., 2006)

The duration of psychosis varies. It can last for only a few days due to extreme experiences, or it can be a feature of a mental health condition such as schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, major depression.

This model essentially suggests that genes involved in neurodevelopment (Jones and Murray, 1991) and/or environmental attacks in early life led to abnormal brain development, which in turn predisposes to the subsequent onset of psychosis (Murray and Lewis, 1987; Bullmore et al., 1998; McDonald et al., 1999). However, the need to refer to the role of social factors such as urban upbringing, social isolation, and migration (Boydell et al., 2004), which point to an interaction between biological and psychological aspects in an increasingly divergent set of development, has also emerged. (Howes et al., 2004). In general, what is observed is the focus on the biological factors that cause and lead to the onset of psychosis. The aim of his article is to elaborate on the psychological factors that affect the onset and course of psychosis, as well as the relationship among them and biological factors.

PSYCHOLOGICAL - ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

1. Anxiety

The influence of anxiety on the onset and course of psychosis is great and essential. From the very beginning, when we tried to define psychosis, we saw that it includes the presence of anxiety disorders, of course, along with other symptoms. Anxiety disorders and anxiety symptoms are common in people with psychotic disorders (Achim et al., 2011; Braga, Reynolds, & Siris, 2013; McEnery, Lim, Tremain, Knowles, & Alvarez - Jimenez, 2019; Temmingh & Stein, 2015). The

experience of stress is usually involved in the onset and maintenance of psychotic disorders. Studies have shown that stress has a negative impact on the severity of positive and negative symptoms, social and overall functioning as well as the overall quality of life (Braga, Mendlowicz, Marrocos, & Figueira, 2005; Huppert, Weiss, Lim, Pratt, & Smith, 2001; Karpov et al., 2017; McEnery et al., 2019; Pallanti, Quercioli, & Hollander, 2004).

Comorbid anxiety is associated with positive and negative symptoms; higher stress levels were associated with greater hallucinations, withdrawal, depression, despair, and poor functioning, as well as better insight (Huppert 2001, Lysaker 2007). The association with positive symptoms is strongest, suggesting that most anxiety is associated with acute exacerbation of schizophrenia (Emsley 1999, Craig 2002). Anxiety is often considered secondary to the psychotic condition and is expected to improve along with schizophrenic symptoms. Anxiety symptoms have a significant negative impact on the quality of life of patients with schizophrenia.

The signs and symptoms of anxiety are the same in patients with psychosis as in patients with anxiety disorders. Sometimes the symptoms of psychosis are more prominent and the symptoms of anxiety do not receive full clinical attention. There is also an overlap of anxiety symptoms and a reaction to the psychotic experience (Braga et al. 2004, Muller et al. 2004). Due to the appearance of stress in a variety of medical conditions, healthcare professionals must detect any routine medical problems or medications behind the stress. Some difficulties in making an accurate diagnosis are usually associated with the effects of drug/alcohol abuse

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

that can mask or reduce the signs and symptoms of anxiety (self-medication) (Castle 2008).

The criteria for the diagnosis of stress in patients with psychosis, include (American Psychiatric Association 1994, Kaplan 1995):

- Severe stress and reduced functioning due to severe stress.
- Experience of diffuse and intense negative emotion, feeling out of control, trapped attention and difficulties in solving a problem.
- physical symptoms of anxiety.
- typical emotional symptoms such as panic, tension, weakness.
- Behavior issues, which are typical of stress and can boost it when avoiding stress, and preventive anxiety.

Anxiety disorders and anxiety symptoms are common in psychosis, although there are differences between cultures. Anxiety symptoms could occur in 60% of patients with chronic psychotic disorder (Siris 1991, Cassano 1999, Morey 1994). Studies have shown that emotional symptoms can predict relapse (Goldberg 1977, Johnson 1988) and suicide risk (Drake 1986, Caldwell 1990). In clinical specimens, the prevalence of obsessive-compulsive disorder in patients with schizophrenia was 15.8% (Kruger 2000), and 23.5% in hospitalized patients with chronic schizophrenia (Poyurovsky 2001). Social phobia is common in patients with schizophrenia. Some studies have shown that approximately 17% of social phobias were associated with psychotic features (Cassano 1998, Cosoff 1998). The nature and severity of social anxiety were similar in schizophrenia and patients with social phobia as their primary diagnosis (Pallanti 2004). Compared to other patients with psychosis, those with social phobia had more suicide attempts with higher mortality and lower social adjustment. Data from various studies have shown that panic attacks are also prevalent in people with schizophrenia (45%). Patients with panic attacks had increased rates of coexisting mental disorder, psychotic symptoms, and use of health services (Goodwin 2002, 2003). Panic attacks are associated with an increased risk of comorbidity of alcohol or substance use disorder. Chen (2001) found that patients with panic attacks had more depressive symptoms, greater hostility, and lower levels of function.

Various diagnostic and standard self-report tests are available to evaluate the symptoms of anxiety. Stress could be investigated by the Beck Hopelessness Scale (Beck 1974), the Beck Anxiety Inventory (Beck 1985), and the Generalized Anxiety Disorder Screener (GAD-7) (Spitzer 2006). For psychological interventions, a careful evaluation of what patients report about their subjective experience and the problems they face is necessary. Research studies have shown that such reports are reliable and consistent even in patients with more severe issues (MacCarthy 1986).

2. Life events

In studies with psychotic disorders, the most common way to measure stress is to approach "life events". Life events are significant life changes that are not uncommon but can occur out of the individual's control (such as the death of a loved one or dismissal from work) or may be influenced by the person's actions (such as divorce or having a child) (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). This approach to measuring stress assumes that some events are associated with a period of adjustment and, often, with some degree of risk, even if the event is positive. When investigating possible causal relationship between the experience of stress and the health outcome, researchers compare the number of life events that occurred before the onset of the disease with the number of events observed during periods of good health (or absence of the condition of interest). A judgment is often made on whether events occur depending on or independent of the health issue being investigated.

It is well known that patients with psychosis have many negative experiences in their lives. Some studies show that people with schizophrenia tend to experience significant stress levels. A history of childhood sexual abuse may predispose some people with schizophrenia to experience substantial statuses of persistent stress. It is not clear whether childhood sexual abuse is more closely linked to specific forms of stress, including symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (Janssen 2004; Lysaker 2005; Lysaker 2007). In addition, cumulative trauma may further increase the risk, given the positive correlation between the number of traumatic experiences and the risk of psychotic illness (Shevlin 2008).

2.1 Retrospective studies

A predominant and innovative study that investigated the relationship between experiencing life events and the onset of a psychotic episode was conducted more than three decades ago. Brown and Birley (1968) reported that people with the pre-existing psychotic disorder had almost twice the number of life events during the three months before admission to a psychiatric ward, compared with a group of the same age. 46% of patients experienced at least one independent event in the three weeks just before the onset of the episode. Still, only 12% experienced an event in any of the three weeks of the previous study period. The incidence rate did not differ during the evaluation period for the comparison team. The authors concluded that there was "reasonable evidence" that although stressful events were not sufficient causes of a psychotic episode on their own, they contributed and probably coincided with other factors to produce the necessary conditions for the onset of the episode and caused episode on average 10 weeks earlier (Brown, Harris, & Peto, 1973). Although the results of this study are often cited as evidence of a causal relationship between the experience of stress and the first onset of a psychotic disorder, such

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

conclusions are erroneous given that participants were mixed, in terms of the number of episodes.

The results of other retrospective studies on the relationship between stressful life events and the onset of a psychotic episode vary. Some have found an increase in the number of life events experienced before the beginning of an acute psychotic episode (Bebbington et al., 1993; Canton & Fraccon, 1985; Chaven & Kulhara, 1988; Day et al., 1987; Mazure, Quinlan & Bowers, 1997; Michaux, Gansereit, McCabe, & Kurland, 1967; Schwartz & Myers, 1977), while others do not (Chung, Langeluddecke, & Tennant, 1986; Gruen & Baron, 1984; Malzacher, Merz, & Ebonther, 1981). Al Khani, Bebbington, Watson, and House (1986) reported that female patients were more likely to report events before the onset of the episode. The same was not observed in male patients. Jacobs and Myers (1976) reported that newly diagnosed patients with schizophrenia had more life events in the year before hospitalization than a healthy control group. Still, this difference was only significant when dependent events were considered. Finally, van Os et al. (1994) reported that people with schizophrenia who had experienced a stressful life event in the three months before the disease onset had milder symptoms, less hospitalization time, and received fewer antipsychotic medications than those who did not.

Recognizing some of the limitations of the life events approach, the experience of "small" events has been evaluated in several studies. Norman and Malla (1993) suggested that people with schizophrenia are more likely to be adversely affected by chronic difficulties and stress experienced under physiological conditions than the most unusually significant life changes and challenges. They showed that the level of discomfort reported by people with schizophrenia was significantly correlated with the number of minor stresses experienced, but not with the number of life events (Norman & Malla, 1991). Similarly, Beck and Worthen (1972) reported that people with schizophrenia are more likely to attribute worsening symptoms to "low-severity" stressors. Some studies have shown that minor stressors or distress are associated with increased comorbid psychotic symptoms such as depression and anxiety.

3. Immigration

Immigration is another situation that provides an opportunity to assess the relationship between stress and the onset of psychotic disorders. Studies focusing on refugees showed that the onset of psychosis is more common in those exposed to extreme stress before immigration (Bhui et al., 2003; Zolkowska, Cantor-Graae, & McNeil, 2003). Other studies have shown that, in some cases, the development of post-migration psychosis is caused by socially disadvantaged stress and is found in a group of cultural minorities in a new environment (Cantor-Graae & Selten, 2005; Hutchinson & Haasen, 2004). One difficulty with immigration studies is that

people who are predisposed to developing schizophrenia or are in the precursor phase may be more likely to move away from where they live (Ödegaard, 1932), although this explanation has recently been challenged (Cantor-Graae & Selten, 2005; Selten, Cantor-Graae, Slaets, & Kahn, 2002).

The risk associated with migration may be exceptionally high in second-generation migrants, migrants from developing countries, and migrants from predominantly black countries. It has been shown that the association between immigration status and psychosis is not solely due to choice (selective migration of people at risk for psychosis). Epidemiological evidence suggests that immigration-related discrimination may be implicated in the risk of developing psychosis, due to the association between the degree of ethnicity discrimination and the relative risk of psychosis.

4. Model of Vulnerability

Although psychotic disorders, such as schizophrenia, are undoubtedly related to biological factors, psychological factors can also influence their onset and course (Arieti, 1974; Bentall, Corcoran, Howard, Blackwood, & Kinderman, 2001; Garety, Kuipers, Fowler, Freeman, & Bebbington, 2001; Kinderman, 2005). Particular attention has been paid to the possible interaction between the experience of "stress" and the course of psychosis. The stress vulnerability model developed by Zubin and Spring (1977) suggests that their understanding of stress is vital for onset of acute psychosis. According to the model, an endogenous, organic mood or vulnerability interacts with internal or external stressors in developing psychotic disorders. Zubin and Spring stated: "Each of us has a degree of vulnerability that, under appropriate conditions, will manifest itself in an episode of schizophrenia" (1977, p. 109). The meaning is that stressful experiences that are not well managed and lead to anxiety and stress can cause psychotic symptoms in people with pre-existing increased vulnerability.

Notably, the model of anxiety vulnerability also creates opportunities for symptom treatment and preventive intervention, primarily through psychological strategies that enhance stress management. For example, researchers in the UK have developed a cognitive psychological model of the role of stressors in the development and maintenance of psychotic symptoms (Freeman, Garety, Kuipers, Fowler, & Bebbington, 2002; Garety et al., 2001). They suggest that the experience of victimization may lead individuals to believe that they are vulnerable and to view the world and others as hostile and threatening. Subsequent stressful events are thought to cause psychotic symptoms under these conditions. Recent studies have supported this model (Dudley & Over, 2003; Freeman et al., 2004), with clear implications for treatment.

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

5. Behavioral Awareness Model in Stress

Awareness refers to the process by which (repeated) exposure to a particular event increases the behavioral and biological response to subsequent exposure to a similar event, even if the subsequent exposure is less severe. The results of such a behavioral awareness process can be increased emotional and psychotic reactions to stress, which occurs when previous exposure to severe or persistent stress results in increased responses to the small stresses of everyday life. Indeed, prior exposure to childhood trauma or life events has been said to increase sensitivity to minor stresses in daily life, which if accumulated may lead to the need for care and impairment of individuals in primary subclinical or schizotypal levels of psychosis.

BIOLOGICAL FACTORS

1. Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis

The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis (HYP) is one of the major stress response systems in the human body. Research on its function shows the biological connection with the psychological factor in the development of psychosis. It is a biological system proposed as a link between the psychological experience of stress and the development of psychosis. The HYE axis is a biological mechanism that

mediates the main adaptive response to perceived psychological or physiological stress.

Nerve signals associated with a stressful event are transmitted in an endocrine response at the hypothalamic level (Figure 2). The supraventricular nucleus in the hypothalamus is a complex integration center that receives and coordinates neuroendocrine, autonomic, cognitive, and emotional energy and is responsible for initiating glucocorticoid secretion. The release of the hormone corticotropin and, to a lesser extent, arginine-vasopressin from the hypothalamic parenchyma is secreted into the pituitary-portal system where they reach the anterior pituitary gland and synergistically stimulate the release of the hormone adrenoprotein. The hormone adrenocorticotropin is then transported into the bloodstream, where it elicits the release of glucocorticoids from the adrenal gland. A negative feedback mechanism ultimately inhibits glucocorticoid release. The glucocorticoid cortisol is an essential mediator of the normal stress response and affects many physiological systems to allow the body to respond to a stressor. Cortisol is a biological stress indicator, the product of the HYP axis in the stress response, and can be obtained through plasma, saliva, and urine. Cortisol has a typical daily rate that can be assessed when samples are collected throughout the day

Figure 2. The ACTH HF axis, adrenocorticotropin hormone AVP, arginine vasopressin; CRF, corticotropin-releasing hormone; GR, glucocorticoid receptors; MR, mineralocorticoid receptors; -ve, negative feedback.

A recently updated Walker and Diforio contribution suggests a "neurological mood-stress model," suggesting that the HPA axis can cause many events that lead to neural circuit dysfunction, including changes in dopamine signaling. This

model is based on data on the effects caused by HYP hormones, in particular cortisol, on the brain and behavior. The authors conclude that several indications show a relationship between HYE axis activity and psychosis. First, diseases associated with elevated cortisol and corticosteroid administration have been observed to cause psychotic symptoms. Second, patients with schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders exhibit HYE dysfunction, such as high

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

levels of cortisol and adrenocorticotrophic hormone, increased cortisol response to pharmacological challenges, and possibly glucocorticoid receptor abnormalities. Furthermore, severe reductions in hippocampal volume, an area of the brain that plays a crucial role in reducing HYP activity, have been described. The volume of the hippocampus is partly determined genetically. Still, the environmental contribution to the volume of the hippocampus is more significant, suggesting a possible role for the stress reactions caused by the HYP. Third, there may be a synergistic relationship between activation of the HYE axis and activation of dopaminergic circuits involved in psychosis. Although the exact mechanisms have not yet been elucidated, evidence suggests that glucocorticoid secretion may increase dopamine activity in certain regions of the brain, particularly the mesolimbic system. Fourth, factors involved in the etiology of schizophrenia, especially prenatal factors, may contribute to HYE dysfunction. These factors include prenatal exposure to maternal stress or glucocorticoid administration, substance use, and various forms of prenatal and perinatal complications.

Survey results

The results of studies that have evaluated the function of the HYE axis in combination with various psychotic disorders through the evaluation of cortisol levels in plasma, urine, or saliva, vary. Higher cortisol levels and abnormal circadian rhythms of cortisol have been reported in patients with schizophrenia compared with healthy controls in some studies but not in others. Compared to other psychiatric patient groups, one study reported that patients with schizophrenia had lower urinary cortisol levels than patients with bipolar disorder and major depressive disorder. However, no differences in salivary cortisol levels between patients with schizophrenia and schizophrenia. disorder in another study. Three studies have reported a blunt cortisol response to psychosocial, psychological, and physical stressors in patients with schizophrenia. The blunt cortisol response to stress may reflect a reduced ability to adapt to stress at the biological level. Once again, it should be noted that some studies had different results. Three studies failed to show any difference in cortisol responses to metabolic stress between patients and controls.

People with major depressive disorder with psychotic features were found to have significantly higher plasma cortisol levels than people with non-psychotic major depressive disorder and healthy controls in a study by Belanoff et al. Also, patients with schizoaffective disorder (manic subtype) had significantly higher plasma cortisol levels than the control group in a Whalley study.

Studies on the neurochemical effects of tetrahydrocannabinol, which is increasingly recognized as a factor that increases the risk of psychosis, show that it increases cortisol release in both non-clinical populations and people with schizophrenia. Stimulants such as amphetamines, associated with an

increased risk of psychosis, also increase cortisol secretion in humans.

In contrast, opiates appear to have little or no psychogenic effect but suppress cortisol secretion in humans. Some studies show that childhood abuse and neglect affect the function of the HR axis. Evidence that childhood trauma is a risk factor for psychosis remains controversial, but early, prolonged, and severe trauma may increase the risk of subsequent psychosis through persistent effects on the HR axis.

The heterogeneous nature of psychotic disorders may explain some of the various effects reported in the studies, mentioned above. For example, some studies have reported that people with schizophrenia who also experience depression or high levels of adverse symptoms are more likely to experience non-suppression of cortisol with the Dexamethasone Suppression Test (DST) by psychotic individuals without any of these symptom profiles. Although not all studies support these findings, methodological differences may explain some of these inconsistencies. The duration of the disease may also be important in determining the function of the HYE axis in relation to psychotic disorders. The duration of psychotic symptoms was negatively correlated with cortisol levels in one study, and HYE axis hyperactivity has been reported more consistently in patients who have recently been hospitalized or are experiencing their first psychotic episode as opposed to patients with chronic disease.

2. Hippocampus

The hippocampus plays a crucial role in the negative feedback loops that ultimately terminate the normal stress response and is particularly important in regulating glucocorticoid levels. In humans, high plasma cortisol levels appear to be associated with reduced hippocampal tumors and cognitive impairment. For example, people with acute Cushing's disease (characterized by chronic high cortisol levels) experience a reduction in hippocampal volume, which is associated with poor performance on verbal memory tests. Decreased hippocampal tumors and deficits in aspects of memory have also been described in naturally healthy elderly individuals with high cortisol levels, and prolonged exposure to cortisol at plasma concentrations similar to those observed during physical and psychological stress has been shown to reduce memory performance. Non-psychiatric patients treated with corticosteroids have been shown to reduce hippocampal volume and impaired knowledge compared with controls. Further evidence of changes in the hippocampus combined with the experience of stress comes from many structural imaging studies that have shown reduced volume in the brain's hippocampus in anxiety disorders such as post-traumatic stress disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder. Finally, treatment of Cushing's disease and subsequent reduction in cortisol levels are associated with increased hippocampal volume.

2.1 Studies

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

Neurocognitive studies strongly suggest that the hippocampus is affected in people with psychotic disorders. People with psychotic disorders usually experience impairments in attention and memory. In addition, hippocampal-dependent verbal memory is a strong predictor of functional outcome.

Studies of brain structure provide more robust evidence for the role of the hippocampus in initiating or maintaining psychosis. One review reported that psychotic disorders were characterized by reductions in hippocampal and Para hippocampal volume, disturbance of hippocampal pyramidal neurons, the smaller size of hippocampal neurons, and lower levels of these proteins at synapses in require further confirmation. Structural neuroimaging studies have repeatedly found reduced hippocampal volume in psychotic patients. These findings are supported by spectroscopy, functional imaging, and shape analysis studies, which have also demonstrated hippocampal abnormalities in schizophrenia. The most substantial results came from high-resolution magnetic resonance imaging studies in patients with chronic schizophrenia, using slices smaller than 1.5 mm. Only one published study of 1.5 mm slices reported no difference in hippocampal volume between schizophrenia and individuals in the control group. The difference in hippocampal tumors is apparent when comparing individuals experiencing a first psychotic episode with the control group. Still, a recent cross-sectional comparative study showed that structural changes in middle temporal regions, including the hippocampus, occur only after the onset of acute episodes of psychosis. The pattern of structural change varies depending on the type of the developing psychosis. This is supported by the results of the only study to date that evaluated the changes in the structure of the brain during the transition to acute psychosis. This study showed that left ventricular parietal, orbital, and cerebral cortices in young people identified as "extremely" at high risk for psychosis decreased after the onset of acute psychosis.

ANXIETY AND COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE

The harmful effects of stress and glucocorticoids on the brain (especially the hippocampus) are well known in the literature, and disorders characterized by increased stress exposure include depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, chronic fatigue disorder, cognitive impairment, especially cognitive impairment in the executive mode. Stress can affect cognitive skills and predispose to psychotic interpretations (Hall, 2017) and affect cognitive performance by attenuating attention control. One study found that stress in the first episode of psychosis was associated with lower speech processing speed but not with memory and programming functions or overall neurocognitive performance (Stouten et al., 2017). In addition, a recent meta-analysis reported a significantly higher prevalence of comorbidity for social anxiety disorder in outpatients than inpatients, leading to a debate about the

potential impact of greater insight and awareness of anxiety symptoms (McEner). et al., 2019). These results suggest that in individuals with good insight - associated with higher cognitive ability (Aleman et al., 2006; Rajji et al., 2014) - stress may develop in possible stigma associated with it (Birchwood et al., 2007).

CONCLUSION

In this article we elaborate the psychological and environmental factors that are associated with the onset of psychosis. The main goal was to highlight the relationship and consequently the interaction between psychological/environmental and biological factors. Stress seems to play a dominant role and combined with other psychological and environmental factors, creates unfavorable conditions for people with psychotic disorders (e.g., migration, psychosocial stress, life events). Stress is joint in patients with psychosis, and its treatment can improve their quality of life. The HYP axis, as already mentioned, is a biological system proposed as a link between the psychological experience of stress and the development of psychosis. The hippocampus is strong evidence for the relationship and interaction between biological and psychological factors. The key points that emerged through our literature review, are: 1) the HR axis is dysfunctional in at least some patients with established psychotic disorders; 2) the hippocampus is an area of the brain that appears to be involved in the onset and maintenance of psychotic disorders; a psychotic episode in some people. There is also some evidence that the onset of psychotic disorders may be associated with higher stress levels and changes in the hippocampus. The hippocampus is an area of the brain that is closely involved in regulating the stress response and may also play a central role in developing and maintaining schizophrenia and other psychoses. Thus, the HYE axis and the hippocampus may mediate between the experience of stressful events and the onset of psychotic illness. Finally, the relationship and interaction are shown by how stress affects cognitive performance and leads to cognitive deficits in patients with psychotic disorders.

REFERENCES

- I. Abs R, Verhelst J, Maeyaert J, et al. Endocrine consequences of long-term intrathecal administration of opioids. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2000;85:2215–2222.
- II. Achim, A. M., Maziade, M., Raymond, E., Olivier, D., Mérette, C., & Roy, M. A. (2011). How prevalent are anxiety disorders in schizophrenia? A meta-analysis and critical review on a significant association. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 37(4), 811– 821.
- III. Addington D, Addington J. Depression dexamethasone non-suppression and negative

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- symptoms in schizophrenia. *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry* 1990; 35:430–433.
- IV. Albus M, Ackenheilo M, Engel RR, Muller F. Situational reactivity of autonomic functions in schizophrenic patients. *Psychiatry Research* 1982; 6:361–370.
- V. Aleman, A., Agrawal, N., Morgan, K.D., David, A.S., 2006. Insight in psychosis and neuropsychological function: meta-analysis. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 189, 204–212 Sep.
- VI. Aleman A, Hijman R, de Haan EH, Kahn RS. Memory impairment in schizophrenia: a meta-analysis. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 1999; 156:1358–1366.
- VII. Al Khani, M. A. S., Bebbington, P. E., Watson, J. P., & House, F. (1986). Life events and schizophrenia: A Saudi Arabian study. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 148, 12–22.
- VIII. Altamura C, Guercetti C, Percudani M. Dexamethasone suppression test in positive and negative schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research* 1989; 30:69–75.
- IX. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and statistical classification of diseases and related health problems* 4th ed. Washington DC: American Psychiatric Association, 1994.
- X. Antonova E, Sharma T, Morris R, Kumari V. The relationship between brain structure and neurocognition in schizophrenia: a selective review. *Schizophrenia Research* 2004; 70:117–145.
- XI. Arieti, S. (1974). An overview of schizophrenia from a predominately psychological approach. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 131, 241–249.
- XII. Bebbington, P., Wilkins, S., Jones, P., Foerster, A., Murray, R., Toone, B., et al. (1993). Life events and psychosis: Initial results from the Camberwell Collaborative Psychosis Study. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 162, 72–79.
- XIII. Beck AT, Emery G & Greenberg RL. *Anxiety disorders and phobias: A cognitive perspective*. New York: Basic Books, 1985.
- XIV. Beck AT, Weismann AW, Lester D, Trexler L. The assessment of pessimism: the hopelessness scale. *J Consult Clin Psychol* 1974; 42:861–865.
- XV. Beck, J., & Worthen, K. (1972). Precipitating stress, crisis theory and hospitalization in schizophrenia and depression. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 26, 123–129.
- XVI. Belanoff JK, Kalehzan M, Fleming-Fick SK, Schatzberg AF. Cortisol activity and cognitive changes in psychotic major depression. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 2001; 158:1612–1616.
- XVII. Bendall S, Jackson HJ, Hulbert CA, McGorry PD. Childhood trauma and psychotic disorders: a systematic, critical review of the evidence. *Schizophr Bull.* 2008;34:568–579.
- XVIII. Bentall, R. P., Corcoran, R., Howard, R., Blackwood, N., & Kinderman, P. (2001). Persecutory delusions: A review and theoretical integration. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 21, 1143–1192.
- XIX. Birchwood, M., Trower, P., Brunet, K., Gilbert, P., Iqbal, Z., Jackson, C., 2007. Social anxiety and the shame of psychosis: a study in first episode psychosis. *Behav. Res.*
- XX. Bhui, K., Abdi, A., Abdi, M., Pereira, S., Dualeh, M., Robertson, D., et al. (2003). Traumatic events, migration characteristics and psychiatric symptoms among Somali refugees: Preliminary communication. *Social Psychiatry & Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 38, 35–43
- XXI. Boog G. Obstetrical complications and subsequent schizophrenia in adolescent and young adult offsprings: is there a relationship? *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2004;114:130–136.
- XXII. Boris Karpov, Tuula Kiesepää, Maija Lindgren, Asko Wegelius, Jaana Suvisaari, Anxiety symptoms in first-episode psychosis. First published: 08 June 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1111/eip.12986>
- XXIII. Boydell, J., van Os, J., McKenzie, K., Murray, R.M., 2004. The association of inequality with the incidence of schizophrenia—an ecological study. *Soc. Psychiatry Psychiatr. Epidemiol.* 39, 597–599.
- XXIV. Braga, R. J., Mendlowicz, M. V., Marrocos, R. P., & Figueira, I. L. (2005). Anxiety disorders in outpatients with schizophrenia: Prevalence and impact on the subjective quality of life. *Journal of Psychiatry Research*, 39(4), 409–414.
- XXV. Braga RJ, Petrides G, Figueira I. Anxiety disorders in schizophrenia. Review. *Compr Psychiatry* 2004; 45(6):460–8.
- XXVI. Braga, R. J., Reynolds, G. P., & Siris, S. G. (2013). Anxiety comorbidity in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research*, 210(1), 1–7.
- XXVII. Brambilla P, Barale F, Caverzasi E, Soares JC. Anatomical MRI findings in mood and anxiety disorders. *Epidemiologia e Psichiatria Sociale* 2002; 11:88–99
- XXVIII. Breier A, Buchanan RW. The effects of metabolic stress on plasma progesterone in

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- healthy volunteers and schizophrenic patients. *Life Science* 1992; 51:1527–1534.
- XXIX. Breier A, Davis OR, Buchanan RW, Moricle LA, Munson RC. Effects of metabolic perturbation on plasma homovanillic acid in schizophrenia: relationship to prefrontal cortex volume. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1993; 50:541–550
- XXX. Breier A, Wolkowitz OM, Doran AR, Bellar S, Pickar D. Neurobiological effects of lumbar puncture stress in psychiatric patients and healthy volunteers. *Psychiatry Research* 1988; 25:187–194.
- XXXI. Brown ES, Woolston D, Frol A et al. Hippocampal volume spectroscopy cognition and mood in patients receiving corticosteroid therapy. *Biological Psychiatry* 2004; 55:538–545.
- XXXII. Brown, G., & Birley, J. (1968). Crises and life changes and the onset of schizophrenia. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 9, 203–214.
- XXXIII. Brown, G. W., Harris, T. O., & Peto, J. (1973). Life events and psychiatric disorders: Part 2: Nature of the causal link. *Psychiatric Medicine*, 3, 159–165.
- XXXIV. Bullmore, E.T., Woodruff, P.W., Wright, I.C., Rabe-Hesketh, S., Howard, R.J., Shuriquie, N., Murray, R.M., 1998. Does dysplasia cause anatomical dysconnectivity in schizophrenia? *Schizophr. Res.* 30, 127–135.
- XXXV. Caldwell J, Gottesman I Schizophrenics kill themselves too. *Schizophr Bull* 1990; 16:571-590.
- XXXVI. Canton, G., & Fraccon, I. G. (1985). Life events and schizophrenia: A replication. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 71, 211–216.
- XXXVII. Cantor-Graae E, Selten JP. Schizophrenia and migration: a meta-analysis and review. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2005;162:12–24.
- XXXVIII. Cassano GB, Pini S, Sacttoni M, Dell'Osso L Multiple anxiety disorder comorbidity in patients with mood spectrum disorders with psychotic features. *Am J Psychiatry* 1999;156(3):474-6.
- XXXIX. Cassano GB, Pini S, Sacttoni M, Rucci P, Dell'Osso L. Occurrence and clinical correlates of psychiatric comorbidity in patients with psychotic disorders. *J Clin Psychiatry* 1998; 59(2):60-68
- XL. Castle DJ. Anxiety and substance use: layers of complexity. Review. *Expert Rev Neurother* 2008; 8(3):493-501.
- XLI. Chaven, B. S., & Kulhara, P. (1988). A clinical study of reactive psychosis. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 78, 712–715.
- XLII. Chen CY, Liu CY, Yang YY. Correlation of panic attacks and hostility in chronic schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Clin Neurosci* 2001; 55(4):383-387.
- XLIII. Christie JE, Whalley LJ, Dick H, Blackwood DHR, Blackburn IM, Fink G. Raised plasma cortisol concentrations a feature of drug-free psychotics and not specific for depression. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1986; 148:58–65
- XLIV. Chung, R. K., Langeluddecke, P., & Tennant, C. (1986). Threatening life events in the onset of schizophrenia, schizophreniform psychosis and hypomania. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 148, 680–685.
- XLV. Cirillo MA, Seidman LJ. Verbal declarative memory dysfunction in schizophrenia: from clinical assessment to genetics and brain mechanisms. *Neuropsychology Review* 2003; 13:43–77.
- XLVI. Copen A, Abou-Saleh M, Milln P, Metcalfe M, Harwood J, Bailey J. Dexamethasone suppression test in depression and other psychiatric illnesses. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1983; 142:498–504.
- XLVII. Coryell W, Lavori P, Endicott J, Keller M, van Eerdewegh M. Outcome in schizoaffective psychotic and non-psychotic depression: course during a six to 24 month follow-up. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1984; 41:787–791.
- XLVIII. Cosoff SJ, Hafner RJ. The prevalence of comorbid anxiety in schizophrenia, schizoaffective and bipolar disorder. *Austr N Z J Psychiatry* 1998; 32 :67-72.
- XLIX. Craig T, Hwang MY, Bromet EJ. Obsessive-compulsive and panic symptoms in patients with first-admission psychosis. *Am J Psychiatry* 2002; 159(4):592-8.
- L. Csernansky JG, Wang L, Jones D et al. Hippocampal deformities in schizophrenia characterized by high dimensional brain mapping. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 2002; 159:2000–2006.
- LI. Czyrak A, Mackowiak M, Chocyk A, Fijal K, Wedzony K. Role of glucocorticoids in the regulation of dopaminergic neurotransmission. *Pol J Pharmacol.* 2003;55:667–674.
- LII. Dallman MF, Akana SF, Strack AM, et al. Chronic stress-induced effects of corticosterone on brain: direct and indirect. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 2004;1018:141–150.

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- LIII. Danessa Mayo, Sarah Corey, Leah H. Kelly, Seghel Yohannes, Alyssa L. Youngquist, Barbara K. Stuart, Tara A. Niendam, Rachel L. Loewy, The Role of Trauma and Stressful Life Events among Individuals at Clinical High Risk for Psychosis: A Review, *Front. Psychiatry*, 20 April 2017 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2017.00055>
- LIV. Day, R., Nielsen, J. A., Korten, A., Ernberg, G., Dube, K. C., Gebhart, J., et al. (1987). Stressful life events preceding the acute onset of schizophrenia: A cross-national study from the World Health Organisation. *Culture, Medicine and Psychiatry*, 11, 123–205.
- LV. Day FL, Valmaggia LR, Mondelli V, Papadopoulos A, Papadopoulos I, Pariante CM, et al. Blunted cortisol awakening response in people at ultra high risk of developing psychosis. *Schizophr Res* (2014) 158(1–3):25–31. doi:10.1016/j.schres.2014.06.041
- LVI. De Bellis MD, Chrousos GP, Dorn LD, et al. Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis dysregulation in sexually abused girls. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 1994;78:249–255.
- LVII. De Haan, Beuk N, Hoogenboom B, Dingemans P, Linszen D. Obsessive-compulsive symptoms observed during treatment with Olanzapine and Risperidone: A prospective study of 113 patients with recent onset schizophrenia or related disorders. *J Clin psychiatry* 2002; 63:104-107.
- LVIII. Dewan MJ, Pandurangi AK, Boucher ML, Levy BF, Major LF. Abnormal dexamethasone suppression test results in chronic schizophrenic patients. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 1982; 139:1501–1503.
- LIX. Drake RE, Cotton PG. Depression and hopelessness and suicide I in chronic schizophrenia. *Br J psychiatry* 1986;148:554-559.
- LX. D'Souza DC, Abi-Saab WM, Madonick S, et al. Delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol effects in schizophrenia: implications for cognition, psychosis, and addiction. *Biol Psychiatry*. 2005;57:594–608.
- LXI. D'Souza DC, Perry E, MacDougall L, et al. The psychotomimetic effects of intravenous delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol in healthy individuals: implications for psychosis. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2004;29:1558–1572.
- LXII. Dudley, R. E. J., & Over, D. E. (2003). People with delusions jump to conclusions: A theoretical account of research findings on the reasoning of people with delusions. *Clinical Psychology and Psychotherapy*, 10, 263–274.
- LXIII. Elman I, Adler CM, Malhotra AK, Bir C, Pickar D, Breier A. Effect of acute metabolic stress on pituitary-adrenal axis activation in patients with schizophrenia. *Am J Psychiatry*. 1998;155:979–981.
- LXIV. Emsley RA, Oosthuisen PP, Joubert AF, Roberts MC, Stein DJ. Depressive and anxiety symptoms in patients with schizophrenia and schizophreniform disorder. *J Clin Psychiatry* 1999; 60:747-751.
- LXV. Freeman, D., Garety, P. A., Kuipers, E., Fowler, D., & Bebbington, P. E. (2002). A cognitive model of persecutory delusions. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 41, 331–347.
- LXVI. Freeman, D., Garety, P. A., Fowler, D., Kuipers, E., Bebbington, P. E., & Dunn, G. (2004). Why do people with delusions fail to choose more realistic explanations for their experiences? An empirical investigation. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 72, 671–680.
- LXVII. Fukuzako H, Yamada K, Kodama S et al. Hippocampal volume asymmetry and age at illness onset in males with schizophrenia. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience* 1997; 247:248–251.
- LXVIII. Garety, P., Kuipers, E., Fowler, D., Freeman, D., & Bebbington, P. E. (2001). A cognitive model of the positive symptoms of psychosis. *Psychological Medicine*, 31, 189–195.
- LXIX. Geuze E, Vermetten E, Bremner JD. MR-based in vivo hippocampal volumetrics: 2. Findings in neuropsychiatric disorders. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2005;10:160–184.
- LXX. Gil-Ad I, Dickerman Z, Amdursky S, Laron Z. Diurnal rhythm of plasma beta endorphin cortisol and growth hormone in schizophrenics compared to control subjects. *Psychopharmacology* 1986; 88:496–499.
- LXXI. Goldberg SC, Schooler NR, Hogarty GE & Colla-borative Study Group: Prediction of relapse in schizophrenic out-patients treated by drugs and sociotherapy. *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 1977; 34:171-184.
- LXXII. Goodwin RD, Amador XF, Malaspina D, Yale SA, Goetz RR, Gorman JM. Anxiety and substance use comorbidity among inpatients with schizophrenia. *Schizophr Res* 2003; 61(1):89-95.
- LXXIII. Goodwin R, Lyons JS, McNally RJ. Panic attacks in Schizophrenia. *Schizophr Res* 2002; 58:213-220.

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- LXXIV. Green MF. What are the functional consequences of neurocognitive deficits in schizophrenia? *American Journal of Psychiatry* 1996; 153:321–330.
- LXXV. Gruen, R., & Baron, M. (1984). Stressful life events and schizophrenia: Relation to illness onset and family history. *Neuropsychobiology*, 12, 206–208
- LXXVI. Hall, J., 2017. Schizophrenia - an anxiety disorder? *Br. J. Psychiatry* 211 (5), 262–263 Nov.
- LXXVII. Harrison PJ. The neuropathology of schizophrenia: a critical review of the data and their interpretation. *Brain* 1999; 122:593–624.121.
- LXXVIII. Heckers S, Konradi C. Hippocampal neurons in schizophrenia. *Journal of Neural Transmission* 2002; 109:891–905.
- LXXIX. Herz MI, Fava GA, Molnar G, Edwards L. The dexamethasone suppression test in newly hospitalised schizophrenic patients. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 1985; 142:127–129.
- LXXX. Howes, O.D., McDonald, C., Cannon, M., Arseneault, L., Boydell, J., Murray, R.M., 2004. Pathways to schizophrenia: the impact of environmental factors. *Int. J. Neuropsychopharmacol.* 7(Suppl. 1), S7–S13.
- LXXXI. Huppert JD, Smith TE. Longitudinal analysis of subjective quality of life in schizophrenia: anxiety as the best symptom predictor. *J Nerv Ment Dis* 2001;189(10):669-75.
- LXXXII. Huppert, J. D., Weiss, K. A., Lim, R., Pratt, S., & Smith, T. E. (2001). Quality of life in schizophrenia: Contributions of anxiety and depression. *Schizophrenia Research*, 51(2-3), 171– 180.
- LXXXIII. Hutchinson, G., & Haasen, C. (2004). Migration and schizophrenia: The challenges for European psychiatry and implications for the future. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 39, 350–357.
- LXXXIV. <https://el.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ψύχωση>
- LXXXV. Jacobs, S., & Myers, J. (1976). Recent life events and acute schizophrenic psychosis: A controlled study. *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 162, 75–87.
- LXXXVI. Jakovljevic M, Mück-Teler D, Pivac N, Crncevic Z. Platelet 5-HT and plasma cortisol concentrations after dexamethasone suppression test in patients with different time course of schizophrenia. *Neuropsychobiology* 1998; 37:142–145.
- LXXXVII. Janssen I, Krabbendam L, Bak M, Hanssen M, Vollebergh W, de Graaf R, van Os J. Childhood abuse as a risk factor for psychotic experiences. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 2004; 109:38–45.
- LXXXVIII. Jansen LMC, Gispen-de Wied CC, Kahn RS. Selective impairments in the stress response in schizophrenic patients. *Psychopharmacology* 2000; 149:319–325.
- LXXXIX. Johnson DAW. The significance of depression in the prediction of relapse in chronic schizophrenia. *Br J Psychiatry* 1988;152:320-323.
- XC. Jones, P., Murray, R.M., 1991. The genetics of schizophrenia is the genetics of neurodevelopment. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 158, 615–623.
- XCI. Joyce EM, Hutton SB, Mutsatsa SH. Cognitive heterogeneity in first-episode schizophrenia. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 2005; 187:516–522.
- XCII. Kahn JP, Rubinow DR, Davis CL, Kling M, Post RM. Salivary cortisol: a practical method for evaluation of adrenal function. *Biol Psychiatry* (1988) 23(4):335–49. doi:10.1016/0006-3223(88)90284-3
- XCIII. Kaplan HI, Sadock BJ. Anxiety disorders. In: Kaplan HI, Sadock BJ, eds. *Comprehensive textbook of psychiatry*. 6th ed. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins, 1995.
- XCIV. Karpov, B., Joffe, G., Aaltonen, K., Suvisaari, J., Baryshnikov, I., Näätänen, P., ... Isometsä, E. (2017). Level of functioning, perceived work ability, and work status among psychiatric patients with major mental disorders. *European Psychiatry*, 44, 83– 89.
- XCV. Kinderman, P. (2005). A psychological model of mental disorder. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 13, 206–217.
- XCVI. Kaneko M, Yokoyama F, Hoshino Y et al. Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis function in chronic schizophrenia: association with clinical features. *Biological Psychiatry* 1992; 25:1–7.
- XCVII. Kofman O. The role of prenatal stress in the etiology of developmental behavioural disorders. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2002;26:457–470.
- XCVIII. Kruger S, Braunig P, Hoffler J, Shugar G, Borner I, Langkrar J. Prevalence of obsessive compulsive disorder in schizophrenia and significance of motor symptoms. *J Neuropsychiatry Clin Neurosci* 2000; 12:16-24.
- XCIX. Kwon JS, Shin YW, Kim CW et al. Similarity and disparity of obsessive-compulsive disorder and schizophrenia in MR volumetric

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- abnormalities of the hippocampus-amygdala complex. *Journal of Neurology Neurosurgery Psychiatry* 2003; 74:962–964.
- C. Lammers CH, Garcia-Borreguero D, Schmider J et al. Combined dexamethasone/corticotropin-releasing hormone test in patients with schizophrenia and in normal controls: II. *Biological Psychiatry* 1995; 38:803–807.
- CI. Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal and coping*. New York: Springer.
- CII. Lisa J. Phillips, Patrick D. McGorry, Belinda Garner, Katherine N. Thompson, Christos Pantelis, Stephen J. Wood, Gregor Berger, Stress, the hippocampus and the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis: implications for the development of psychotic disorders, *Aust N Z J Psychiatry*. 2006 Sep;40(9):725-41. doi: 10.1080/j.1440-1614.2006.01877.x.
- CIII. Lisa J Phillips, Shona M Francey, Jane Edwards, Nancy McMurray, Stress and psychosis: towards the development of new models of investigation, *Clin Psychol Rev*. 2007 Apr;27(3):307-17. doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2006.10.003.
- CIV. Lopez JF, Akil H, Watson SJ. Neural circuits mediating stress. *Biological Psychiatry* 1999; 46:1461–1471.
- CV. Lupien S, Lecours AR, Lussier I, Schwartz G, Nair NP, Meaney MJ. Basal cortisol levels and cognitive deficits in human aging. *Journal of Neuroscience* 1994; 14:2893–2903.
- CVI. Lysaker PH, Davis LW, Gattton MJ, Herman SM. Associations of anxiety-related symptoms with reported history of childhood sexual abuse in schizophrenia spectrum disorders. *J Clin Psychiatry* 2005; 66(10):1279-84.
- CVII. Lysaker PH, Salyers MP. Anxiety symptoms in schizophrenia spectrum disorders: associations with social function, positive and negative symptoms, hope and trauma history. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 2007;116(4):290-8.
- CVIII. McCarley RW, Shenton ME, O'Donnell BF et al. Auditory P300 abnormalities and left posterior superior temporal gyrus volume reduction in schizophrenia. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1993; 50:190–197.
- CIX. McCarley RW, Wible CG, Frumin M, Hirayasu Y, Fischer IA, Shenton ME. MRI anatomy of schizophrenia. *Biological Psychiatry* 1999; 45:1085–1098.
- CX. MacCarthy B, Benson J, Brewin CR. Task motivation and problem appraisal in long-term psychiatric patients. *Psychol Med* 1986; 16:431-438.
- CXI. Maija Lindgren, Heli Birling, Tuula Kiesepää, Annamari Tuulio-Henriksson, Is cognitive performance associated with anxiety and depression in first-episode psychosis? Volume 263, 15 February 2020, Pages 221-227, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2019.11.161>
- CXII. Malaspina D, Perera GM, Lignelli A et al. SPECT imaging of odor identification in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research* 1998; 82:53–61
- CXIII. Malzacher, M., Merz, J., & Ebonther, D. (1981). Einscheidende lebensereignisse im vorfeld akuter schizophrener episoden. *Archiv für Psychiatrie und Nervenkrankheiten*, 230, 227–242.
- CXIV. Marinelli M, Rudick CN, Hu XT, White FJ. Excitability of dopamine neurons: modulation and physiological consequences. *CNS Neurol Disord Drug Targets*. 2006;5:79–97.
- CXV. Matthew R Broome, James B Woolley, Paul Tabraham, Louise C Johns, Elvira Bramon, Graham K Murray, Carmine Pariante, Philip K McGuire, Robin M Murray, What causes the onset of psychosis? *Schizophr Res*. 2005 Nov 1;79(1):23-34. doi: 10.1016/j.schres.2005.02.007.
- CXVI. Mazure, C. M., Quinlan, D. M., & Bowers, M. B. (1997). Recent life stressors and biological markers in newly admitted psychotic patients. *Biological Psychiatry*, 41, 865–870.
- CXVII. McDonald, C., Fearon, P., Murray, R., 1999. Neurodevelopmental Hypothesis of Schizophrenia 12 years on: Data and Doubts. In: Rapoport, J. (Ed.), *Childhood Onset of Adult Psychopathology* American Psychiatric Press, Washington, pp. 193–220.
- CXVIII. McEnery, C., Lim, M. H., Tremain, H., Knowles, A., & Alvarez-Jimenez, M. (2019). Prevalence rate of social anxiety disorder in individuals with a psychotic disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Schizophrenia Research*, 208, 25–33.
- CXIX. McEwen BS, De Kloet ER, Rostene W. Adrenal steroids receptors and actions in the nervous system. *Physiology Review* 1986; 66:1121–1188.
- CXX. Meltzer HY, Lee MA, Jayathilake K. The blunted plasma cortisol response to apomorphine and its relationship to treatment response in patients with schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2001; 24:278–290.

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- CXXI. Michaux, W. W., Gansereit, K. H., McCabe, O. L., & Kurland, A. A. (1967). Psychopathology and measurement of environmental stress. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 3, 358–372.
- CXXII. Minas I, Jackson HJ, Joshua S, Burgess P. Depression negative and positive symptoms and the DST in schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Research* 1990; 5–6:321–327
- CXXIII. Moghaddam B. Stress activation of glutamate neurotransmission in the prefrontal cortex: implications for dopamine-associated psychiatric disorders. *Biol Psychiatry*. 2002;51:775–787.
- CXXIV. Mojca Zvezdana Dernovšek I & Lilijana Šprah, COMORBID ANXIETY IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOSIS. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 2009; Vol. 21, Suppl. 1, pp 43–50
- CXXV. Monica Aas, Paola Dazzan, Valeria Mondelli, Ingrid Melle, Robin M. Murray, Carmine M. Pariante, A systematic review of cognitive function in first-episode psychosis, including a discussion on childhood trauma, stress, and inflammation, *Front. Psychiatry*, 08 January 2014 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2013.00182>
- CXXVI. Monteleone P, Piccolo A, Martino M, Maj M. Seasonal variation in the dexamethasone suppression test: a longitudinal study in chronic schizophrenics and in healthy subjects. *Neuropsychobiology* 1994; 30:61–65.
- CXXVII. Moore TH, Zammit S, Lingford-Hughes A, et al. Cannabis use and risk of psychotic or affective mental health outcomes: a systematic review. *Lancet*. 2007;370:319–328.
- CXXVIII. Moorey H, Soni SD. Anxiety symptoms in stable chronic schizophrenic. *J Ment Health* 1994; 3:257-262.
- CXXIX. Mück-Seler D, Pivac N, Jakovljevic M, Brzovic Z. Platelet serotonin plasma cortisol and dexamethasone suppression test in schizophrenic patients. *Biological Psychiatry* 1999; 45:1433–1439
- CXXX. Muck-Seler D, Pivac N, Mustapic M, Crncevic Z, Jakovljevic M, Sagud M. Platelet serotonin and plasma prolactin and cortisol in healthy, depressed and schizophrenic women. *Psychiatry Res*. 2004;127:217–226.
- CXXXI. Muller JE, Koen L, Soraya S, Emsley RA, Stein DJ. Anxiety disorders and schizophrenia. Review. *Curr Psychiatry Rep* 2004;6(4):255-61.
- CXXXII. Murray, R.M., Lewis, S.W., 1987. Is schizophrenia a neuro-developmental disorder? *Br. Med. J. (Clin. Res. Ed.)* 295,681–682.
- CXXXIII. Newcomer JW, Faustman WO, Whiteford HA, Moses JA, Csernansky JG. Symptomatology and cognitive impairment associate independently with post-dexamethasone cortisol concentrations in unmedicated schizophrenia patients. *Biological Psychiatry* 1991; 29:855–864.
- CXXXIV. Newcomer JW, Selke G, Melson AK et al. Decreased memory performance in healthy humans induced by stress-level cortisol treatment. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1999; 56:527–533.
- CXXXV. Norman, R. M. G., & Malla, A. K. (1991). Subjective stress in schizophrenic patients. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 26, 212–216.
- CXXXVI. Norman, R. M. G., & Malla, A. K. (1993). Stressful life events and schizophrenia: I: A review of the research. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 162, 161–166.
- CXXXVII. O'Brien JT. The 'glucocorticoid cascade' hypothesis in man. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1997; 170:199–201.
- CXXXVIII. Ödegaard, Ö. (1932). Emigration and insanity. *Acta Psychiatrica Neurologica Scandinavica Supplementum*, 4, 1–206.
- CXXXIX. Oswald LM, Wong DF, McCaul M, et al. Relationships among ventral striatal dopamine release, cortisol secretion, and subjective responses to amphetamine. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2005;30:821–832.
- CXL. Pallanti, S., Quercioli, L., & Hollander, E. (2004). Social anxiety in outpatients with schizophrenia: A relevant cause of disability. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 161(1), 53–58.
- CXLI. Pantelis C, Velakoulis D, McGorry PD et al. Neuroanatomical abnormalities before and after onset of psychosis: a cross-sectional and longitudinal MRI study. *Lancet* 2003; 361:281–288.
- CXLII. Pariante CM, Vassilopoulou K, Velakoulis D et al. Abnormal pituitary volume in psychosis. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 2004; 185:5–10
- CXLIII. Pivac N, Mück-Teler D, Jakovljevic M. Platelet 5-HT levels and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis activity in schizophrenic patients with positive and negative symptoms. *Neuropsychobiology* 1997; 36:19–21.
- CXLIV. Porter RJ, Gallagher P, Thompson JM, Young AH. Neurocognitive impairment in drug-free patients with major depressive disorder. *Br J Psychiatry* (2003) 182:214–20. doi:10.1192/bjp.182.3.214

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- CXLV. Poyurovsky M, Hramenkov S, Isakov V, Rauchverger B, Modai I, Schneidam M, Fuchs C, Weizman A. Obsessive-compulsive disorder in hospitalized patients with chronic schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Res* 2001; 102:49-57.
- CXLVI. Rajji, T.K., Miranda, D., Mulsant, B.H., 2014. Cognition, function, and disability in patients with schizophrenia: a review of longitudinal studies. *Can. J. Psychiatry* 59 (1), 13–17 Jan.
- CXLVII. Rao ML, Strelbel B, Halaris A et al. Circadian rhythm of vital signs norepinephrine epinephrine thyroid hormones and cortisol in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research* 1995; 57:21–39.
- CXLVIII. Riley EM, McGovern D, Mockler D et al. Neuropsychological functioning in first-episode psychosis: evidence of specific deficits. *Schizophrenia Research* 2000; 43:47–55.
- CXLIX. Ruud van Winkel, Nicholas C. Stefanis, Inez Myin-Germeys Psychosocial Stress and Psychosis. A Review of the Neurobiological Mechanisms and the Evidence for Gene-Stress Interaction *Schizophr Bull.* 2008 Nov; 34(6): 1095–1105. Published online 2008 Aug 20. doi: 10.1093/schbul/sbn101
- CL. Ryan MC, Sharifi N, Condren R, Thakore JH. Evidence of basal pituitary-adrenal overactivity in first episode, drug naive patients with schizophrenia. *Psychoneuroendocrinology.* 2004;29:1065–1070.
- CLI. Saffer D, Metcalfe M, Coppen A. Abnormal dexamethasone suppression test in Type II schizophrenia. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1985; 147:721–723
- CLII. Sandstrom A, Rhodin IN, Lundberg M, Olsson T, Nyberg L. Impaired cognitive performance in patients with chronic burnout syndrome. *Biol Psychol* (2005) 69:271–9. doi:10.1016/j.biopsycho.2004.08.003
- CLIII. Sapolsky RM, Krey LC, McEwen BS. The neuroendocrinology of stress and aging: the glucocorticoid cascade hypothesis. *Endocr Rev* (1986) 7:284–301. doi:10.1210/edrv-7-3-284
- CLIV. Sapolsky RM. The possibility of neurotoxicity in the hippocampus in major depression: a primer on neuron death. *Biol Psychiatry* (2000) 48:755–65. doi:10.1016/S0006-3223(00)00971-9
- CLV. Schwartz, C. C., & Myers, J. K. (1977). Life events and schizophrenia: II: Impact of life events on symptom configuration. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 34, 1242–1245.
- CLVI. Sheline YI, Sanghavi M, Mintun MA, Gado MH. Depression duration but not age predicts hippocampal volume loss in medically healthy women with recurrent major depression. *Journal of Neuroscience* 1999; 19:5034–5043.
- CLVII. Selten, J. P., Cantor-Graae, E., Slaets, J., & Kahn, R. S. (2002). Odegaard's selection hypothesis revisited: Schizophrenia in Surinamese immigrants to The Netherlands. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 159, 669–671
- CLVIII. Sharma T, Antonova L. Cognitive function in schizophrenia: deficits functional consequences and future treatment. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America* 2003; 26:25–40.
- CLIX. Shenton ME, Gerig G, McCarley RW, Szekely G, Kikinis R. Amygdala-hippocampal shape differences in schizophrenia: the application of 3D shape models to volumetric MR data. *Psychiatry Research* 2002; 115:15–35.
- CLX. Shenton ME, Kikinis R, Jolesz FA et al. Abnormalities of the left temporal lobe and thought disorder in schizophrenia: a quantitative magnetic resonance imaging study. *New England Journal of Medicine* 1992; 327:604–612.
- CLXI. Shevlin M, Houston JE, Dorahy MJ, Adamson G. Cumulative traumas and psychosis: an analysis of the national comorbidity survey and the British Psychiatric Morbidity Survey. Review. *Schizophr Bull* 2008; 34(1):193-9.
- CLXII. Siris SG: Diagnosis of secondary depression in schizophrenia. *Schizophr Bull* 1991; 17:75-89.
- CLXIII. Spitzer RL, Kroenke K, Williams JB, Löwe B. A brief measure for assessing generalized anxiety disorder: the GAD-7. *Arch Intern Med* 2006;166(10):1092-7.
- CLXIV. Starkman MN, Gebarski SS, Berent S, Schteingart DE. Hippocampal formation volume memory dysfunction and cortisol levels in patients with Cushing's syndrome. *Biological Psychiatry* 1992; 32:756–765.
- CLXV. Starkman MN, Giordani B, Gebarski SS, Berent S, Schork MA, Schteingart DE. Decrease in cortisol reverses human hippocampal atrophy following treatment of Cushing's disease. *Biological Psychiatry* 1999; 46:1595–1602
- CLXVI. Steen RG, Mull C, McClure R, Hamer RM, Lieberman JA. Brain volume in first-episode schizophrenia: systematic review and meta-analysis of magnetic resonance imaging studies. *Br J Psychiatry.* 2006;188:510–518.
- CLXVII. Stein MB, Koverola C, Hanna C, Torchia MG, McClarty B. Hippocampal volume in women

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

- victimized by childhood sexual abuse. *Psychological Medicine* 1997; 27:951–959.
- CLXVIII. Stouten, L.H., Veling, W., Laan, W., van der Helm, M., van der Gaag, M., 2017. Psychosocial functioning in first-episode psychosis and associations with neurocognition, social cognition, psychotic and affective symptoms. *Early Interv. Psychiatry* 11, 23–36.
- CLXIX. Szeszko PR, Robinson D, Alvir JM et al. Orbital frontal and amygdala volume reductions in obsessive-compulsive disorder. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1999; 56:913–919
- CLXX. Talbot PS. The molecular neuroimaging of anxiety disorders. *Current Psychiatry Reports* 2004; 6:274–279.
- CLXXI. Tandon R, Mazzara C, DeQuardo J et al. Dexamethasone suppression test in schizophrenia: relationship to symptomatology ventricular enlargement and outcome. *Biological Psychiatry* 1991; 29:953–964.
- CLXXII. Tarullo AR, Gunnar MR. Child maltreatment and the developing HPA axis. *Horm Behav.* 2006;50:632–639.
- CLXXIII. Temmingh, H., & Stein, D. J. (2015). Anxiety in patients with schizophrenia: Epidemiology and management. *CNS Drugs*, 29(10), 819– 832.
- CLXXIV. van Erp TG, Saleh PA, Huttunen M, et al. Hippocampal volumes in schizophrenic twins. *Arch Gen Psychiatry.* 2004;61:346–353.
- CLXXV. van Haren NE, Picchioni MM, McDonald C, et al. A controlled study of brain structure in monozygotic twins concordant and discordant for schizophrenia. *Biol Psychiatry.* 2004;56:454–461.
- CLXXVI. van Os, J., Fahy, P., Bebbington, P., Jones, P., Wilkins, S., Sham, P., et al. (1994). The influence of life events on the subsequent course of psychotic illness: A prospective follow-up of the Camberwell Collaborative Psychosis Study. *Psychological Medicine*, 24, 503–513.
- CLXXVII. Velakoulis D, Pantelis C, McGorry PD et al. Hippocampal volume in first-episode psychoses and chronic schizophrenia: a high resolution Magnetic Resonance Imaging study. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1999; 56:133–140.
- CLXXVIII. Velakoulis D, Wood SJ, Wong MTH et al. Hippocampal and amygdala volumes differ according to psychosis stage and diagnosis: an MRI study of chronic schizophrenia first-episode psychosis and ultra-high risk subjects. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 2006; 63:139–149.
- CLXXIX. Veling W, Selten JP, Susser E, Laan W, Mackenbach JP, Hoek HW. Discrimination and the incidence of psychotic disorders among ethnic minorities in The Netherlands. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2007;36:761–768.
- CLXXX. Walder DJ, Walker EF, Lewine RJ. Cognitive functioning cortisol release and symptom severity in patients with schizophrenia. *Biological Psychiatry* 2000; 48:1121–1132.
- CLXXXI. Walker EF, Diforio D. Schizophrenia: a neural diathesis-stress model. *Psychol Rev.* 1997;104:667–685.
- CLXXXII. Walker E, Mittal V, Tessner K. Stress and the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal axis in the developmental course of schizophrenia. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol.* 2008;4:189–216.
- CLXXXIII. Walsh P, Spelman L, Sharifi N, Thakore JH. Male patients with paranoid schizophrenia have greater ACTH and cortisol secretion in response to metoclopramide-induced AVP release. *Psychoneuroendocrinology.* 2005;30:431–437.
- CLXXXIV. Weber DL, Clark CR, McFarlane AC, Moores KA, Morris P, Egan GF. Abnormal frontal and parietal activity during working memory updating in post-traumatic stress disorder. *Psychiatry Res (2005)* 140:27–44. doi:10.1016/j.psychresns.2005.07.003
- CLXXXV. Weiss AP, Heckers S. Neuroimaging of declarative memory in schizophrenia. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology* 2001; 42:239–250.
- CLXXXVI. Whalley LJ, Christie JE, Blackwood DH et al. Disturbed endocrine function in the psychoses. I: Disordered homeostasis or disease process? *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1989; 155:455–461
- CLXXXVII. Whiteford H, Riney S, Savaia R, Csernansky J. Dexamethasone non-suppression test in chronic schizophrenia. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica* 1988; 77:58–62.
- CLXXXVIII. Wright IC, Rabe-Hesketh S, Woodruff PW, David AS, Murray RM, Bullmore ET. Meta-analysis of regional brain volumes in schizophrenia. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 2000; 157:16–25.
- CLXXXIX. Yehuda R, Boisoneau D, Mason JW, Giller EL. Glucocorticoid receptor number and cortisol secretion in mood anxiety and psychotic disorders. *Biological Psychiatry* 1993; 34:18–25.
- CXC. Yehuda R, Southwick SM, Nussbaum G, Wahby V, Giller EL Jr, Mason JW. Low urinary cortisol excretion in patients with posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease* 1990; 178:366–369.
- CXCI. Yeragani VK. The incidence of abnormal dexamethasone suppression in schizophrenia: a

The Beginning of Psychosis: Psychological and Environmental Factors That Lead To Psychosis and Their Relationship to Biological Factors

review and a meta-analytic comparison with the incidence in normal controls. *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry* 1990; 35:128–132.

- CXCII. Zolkowska, K., Cantor-Graae, E., & McNeil, T. F. (2003). Psychiatric admissions for psychosis in Malmo during the NATO bombing of Kosovo. *Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 191, 820–826.
- CXCIII. Zubin, J., & Spring, B. (1977). Vulnerability: A new view of schizophrenia. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 86, 103–126.